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Abstract: *In this article, typical and retail relationships are studied in various aspects. Information is also received about the nature of typical relationships and retail trade. It has been proven that typical relationships allow the choice of the necessary unit when using the language, as well as forming forms and words according to measurement. Or a series of elements of the same arrangement for a specific length, side by side, one by one, on a scientific basis.*

Keywords: *paradigmatic relations, syntagmatic relations, speech chain, phoneme, morpheme, horizontal, vertical, morph, word forms, sentence, paradigm, syntagma.*

Paradigmatic relationships include groups and categories such as consonant systyl systyl systems, which allow paradigmatic relations, as well as forms and words can be compatibility relations with the same level of speech, morpheme, etc. Including two or more units compares a horizontal connection with a particular relationship with a particular relationship. With other content, together with another content, K-I-T-O-B (phonological methods-Monological); QA-LAM, DAF-tar (via morphological method); Kitob-Xon, Gul-Chi (according to word training method); Toza Havoya (by syntactic method). According to paradigmatic dictionaries, without the identity relationship of paradigmatic languages, that is, a paradigm combines a set of language units similar to one of other criteria. Paradigmatically, one or another language unit belongs to which group of the grammatical group by comparing it with similar ones. In paradigmatic relationships, a unit in the language, such as morph and morpheme, the same word forms, and the same sentence forms, occurs in the relationship between different forms. In paradigmatic relationships of word forms and syntactic structures, different grammatical meanings of the same unit are revealed. For example, in the agreement paradigm of the noun, different meanings of its forms are given (book, book, to book); or, in the verb's conjugation scheme, different meanings of its forms are given. A model is a set of relationships between units that can substitute each other in the same situation. Red apple (yellow, green), etc. are examples. In this case, yellow and green

are reduced to one dominant row. The systematic study of the language is designed to establish the relationship between the elements and units of the language in a paradigmatic and syntagmatic manner. Language units are arranged in a parallel sequence by symbiotic relationships. Words are organized into a series of morphemes and syllables, words, phrases, clauses, and complex syntactic structures in syntagmatic relationships. Syntagmatic relationships, in language usage, allow the simultaneous use of two or more words.

Paradigmatic and syntagmatic relationships are horizontal, while syntagmatic relationships are distinguished by their location in a vertical row. Ferdinand de saussure (1857-1913)'s scientific theory is based on the fact that language is a multifaceted phenomenon with a host of interesting contradictions. According to f. de saussure, the subject of linguistics research should be speech study. F. de saussure demonstrated for the first time that speech production is a unit made up of words and phrases. Linguistics should therefore examine language and expression as well as speech production. F. de saussure made an absolute distinction between words and sounds, stressing that they are distinct phenomena. With ferdinand saussure's name, the difference between paradigmatic and syntagmatic relationships is apparent. The syntagmatic relationship is based on the linear nature of the language, which does not allow two words to be pronounced at the same time, according to saussure. In the speech sequence, these elements are arranged one after the other, creating compounds called syntagms. This term refers not only to terms, but also to word combinations, complex units of any length (compound words, artificial words, and sentences). A term is only meaningful when it contrasts with what precedes it, what follows it, or both. A syntagma is an intonation-semantic term that describes one idea in a particular context and situation, and may be expressed as a word, a phrase, or a whole sentence. Syntagmatics refers to linguistic rules that determine the compatibility of language units of one level and their application in speech. The following example illustrates the difference between syntagmatics and paradigmatics. On the one hand, the word book reminds of other forms of the given word (book, my book, from the book, etc.). And semantically close words (to read, to study, to read). The book and its named forms are combined into a particular style of classification and paradigm. The term "book" and nouns that are closely related to it in terms of meaning are a pair of terms that form a synonym group formed on the basis of paradigmatic relationships of lexical meanings. On the other hand, the term book can be used to describe a book in terms of verbs, nouns, and adjectives: an informative book; to read a book; art book, etc. The following

expressions reveal the structure and semantic relationships of words that are based on syntagmatic relationships.

The relationship between words and each other, i.e., their linear arrangement, is a syntagmatic relationship. Grammatical units of the language form relationships by entering into specific relationships with each other. These relationships are of two types: the first is that successive units are connected in a chain, i.e. linear relationships; the second is that unit relationships, i.e. non-linear relationships, are formed by continuous changes of one unit. To determine syntagmatic relationships, special techniques of syntagmatic analysis have been developed. They consist of methods of distinguishing linguistic sequences and determining their structure, as well as special methods of determining the relationship of one unit to another, which are particularly apparent in phonology and morphology, according to saussure. A syntagmatic relationship consists of two or more components of the relationship that are identical in the real sequence.

Ferdinand de saussure compares a syntagmatic relationship to a rectilinear column, which is a particular relationship based on the hypothesis he supports. Linear relationships are referred to as syntagmatic relationships, while non-linear relationships are referred to as paradigmatic relationships. In syntagmatic relationships, important parts of units are included, such as stems and affixes, words, etc. In the process of forming a sentence, syntagmatic relationships between words and word forms, between word combinations, are expressed in the process of forming a sentence. At the same time, many units can form syntagmatic relationships. A complex syntactic device and an extended text are formed on the basis of these relationships, which are expressed in terms. Syntagm belongs to speech, not to speech, according to ferdinand de saussure. Although the key parts can be distinguished, the language contains ready-made expressions in which custom prohibits any modification. When used in writing, the form of these terms varies according to the particular meanings or syntax. Language units are in direct contact with each other and form a whole system dependent on each other. "the relationship of language units with the weight of their content arises in two directions that form separate lines," f. de saussure said. Comparing these directions helps us to understand the nature of each one. They require two forms of our physical activity, on which the development and existence of language are dependent." It can be seen that f. de saussure refers to the unital and syntagmatic relationships of the language system.

However, it should also be noted that the paradigmatic relationship should not be confused with language and the syntagmatic relationship to speech. Both of them are

present in the structure of language units. Such types of syntagms were linked to the language by a scientist who used to use such rules. Such types of documents are only permitted if the language has enough copies of them registered. Saussure came to the conclusion that it is difficult to decide whether one or another syntagm is related to speech or language syntagmatically. Because the boundary between the fact of speech and the fact of speech, which is dependent on individual rights, is blurred. Both factors may have been involved in the formation of the syntagma, and it is impossible to determine in this case.

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